

As on 23-01-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended to add record of crops utilisation status into the knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to understand the context of the utilisation status of the crops in a specific location. In several sources and deduce the classification based on the provided information.
2. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. There are six fields to be entered, four of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

1.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the crop common name.
- Choose the **RIGHT** crop name in Crop ID. Since the common name is used in Crop ID, make sure to check the scientific name of the crop in Crop Records. Crop scientific name **MUST** be similar as stated in the data source.

1.2 Location (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the location of the crops. Location **MUST** be recorded according to the region/country/place where the crop is being underutilised/major crop/found-in or grown based on the data source.
- Multiple locations can be recorded by using the same metadata ID record if there is more than one location stated in the data source.
- If there is no specific location stated in the data source, location should be entered **GLOBAL**.

1.3 Utilisation status (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the status of the crop, which are divided into four groups:
 - I. Underutilised - referring to the crops that are mentioned in the sources to be underutilised in a specified location.
 - II. Major crop - Referring to the crops with high production in a specified location. Usually they are regarded as major crops by the organisation with authorities i.e. Department of Agriculture.
 - III. Grown/Found in - Referring to the crops that were mentioned in the sources to be grown or found in a specific location.
 - IV. Unspecified - Referring to the crops evidence of the utilisation status is nowhere to be found.
- One must choose the **RIGHT** utilisation status of the crops which are mentioned in the sources to be underutilised/major/found-in or grown in a specific location.

1.4 Source year

- This is referring to the year of data being published.

1.5 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop itself.

1.6 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to its metadata.
- One **MUST** create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.